

Methodology of developing creative ability of students in painting classes

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Abstract: In this article, the use of art therapy, which is a popular method of psychological correction of emotional disorders, the role and importance of art therapy sessions in the development of a person, as well as the problems of developing their emotional and personal sphere, the factors necessary for personality development, and issues of revealing the possibilities of using art and art therapy methods in finding effective methods of neutralizing negative influencing resources and anomalous functions of personality.

Key words: art therapy, emotional disorders, emotions, aggression, psychological correction, creative ability, personality, aesthetic skills, perception, anomalous function.

Personality development is a period of development that requires serious attention not only from parents, but also from educators. During this period, social skills and norms of behavior, moral values, among others, "self-recognition", problems in communication not only in the family, but also with peers, conflicting processes of interaction in society are encountered. Of course, the level of development of his emotional and moral sphere depends on his mental health. Therefore, the development of the emotional sphere of personality through creation, the conditions for the formation of emotional intelligence, emotional sensitivity and empathy is one of the urgent problems of today. Unfortunately, nowadays, more attention is paid to intellectual development in the field of education than to the development of the emotional and personal sphere. This leads to the fact that in the modern programs of educational institutions this issue is not included in the program documents, or it is fragmented and solved in an unsystematic way. The big psychological dictionary gives the following description of emotions: "Emotions (Latin *eshowege* - to arouse, excite) - mental processes associated with instincts, needs, motives and reflected in the form and is a special class of situations (people and animals). Events and situations that affect a person are of great importance in the realization of his life. Mental activity and behavior aimed at satisfying urgent needs that accompany almost any manifestation of the subject's activity. serves as one of the main mechanisms of internal regulation of actions. It is known that art therapy is based on the effective use of art and creativity, and is one of the directions of psychological correction. In a word, art therapy is usually visual art therapy aimed at influencing the psycho-emotional state of a person. The main goal of art therapy is to harmonize the state of mind by developing self-expression and "self-awareness". Usually, the importance of using art for therapeutic purposes is that it can be used to symbolically express and explore different emotions: love, hate, sadness, anger, fear, joy, etc.

For example, the technique of art therapy is based on the conclusion that the content of the inner "I" of a person is reflected in the visual images he draws or sculpts. Basically, the state of the psyche changes. As for the term art therapy, it literally means "treatment with art." The term was first coined by artist Adrian Hill in 1938 to describe his work with tuberculosis patients in sanatoriums. Art therapy methods were first used in the United States during the Second World War with children who were under psychological pressure taken from Nazi camps. Art therapy originally reflects the psychoanalytic views of Z. Freud and K. G. Jung, according to which the final product of the client's artistic activity (whether it is a drawing, sculpture, assembly) represents his unconscious mental processes. The results achieved led to the establishment of the American Art Therapy Association in 1969. It is known that the main goal of art therapy is to master the

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VOLUME-3, ISSUE-5

process of self-knowledge in a person and to develop his ability to express himself, and its concept currently includes several meanings: - a set of art used in treatment and correction; - a set of art therapy techniques; - direction of psychotherapeutic and psychorexia practice; - art therapy methods. The development of personal feelings is influenced not only by the family, but also by certain life situations. Any changes in the usual lifestyle (daily routine, etc.) or a negative social situation can lead to the manifestation of affective reactions, including increased fear. Needs, a feeling of social insecurity, anxiety, especially during the age crisis, leads to a state of despair (anger, aggression or, on the contrary, a state of passivity) and leads to an increase in characteristics such as aggression. Aggression should be understood as any intentional behavior that harms another person or thing. There are the following types of aggression: physical (attacking, hitting, biting) and verbal (shouting, cursing). In addition, instrumental and targeted aggression are different. The most aggressive actions are instrumental aggression, that is, stopping at nothing for personal gain. To strengthen this position, they use physical aggression. Targeted aggression is always planned and directed. So, aggression is harming another person or object for a specific purpose. Aggression can be situational, that is, it is episodic and personal in a certain situation, and it is manifested in the form of stable behavior under suitable conditions. The qualities of aggression appear in the child's behavior in exactly 6 months, such as lack of self-control, non-compliance with rules, hysterical behavior (often demonstrative), insulting behavior towards peers and adults, blaming others for their mistakes if there is, then in such a case the child is considered an aggressor. Unfortunately, when an aggressive child is tried to have an educational influence, a kind of circle is created, and the aggressive child creates a hostile attitude towards him from others, as a result of which his aggressive actions increase, because they support him in aggression. powered up. The emotional burden and demands of the parents on the child, if they do not correspond to his age, lead to the fact that the child is forced to protect the preservation of "his boundaries". The emotional sphere of a person with a complex regulatory system is very weak, but it takes the first place in the formation of personality and affects the formation of behavior.

The role of art therapy is incomparable in the correction and treatment of anomalous functions in such development with the help of art. Currently, in our country, there are opportunities for the use of art therapy for children of preschool age, but it is not intended to be used as a practical exercise in art classes and clubs in general education schools. , and within the framework of fine arts in higher educational institutions, these issues have not been given serious attention and have not been formed as an academic subject. The use of art therapy technologies in the field of education successfully solves the problems of creating conditions for the emotional development of a person, as well as preventing and correcting negative emotional manifestations. Therefore, art therapy is an independent psychotherapeutic direction that has a corrective effect through visual and creative activities in order to harmonize and develop the human psyche. The definition of art therapy is based on the concepts of expression, communication, and symbolism associated with artistic creativity. The use of art therapy in correction and treatment with the help of art means to prevent today's negative processes affecting the human psyche (wars, natural disasters, overcoming infectious diseases, aggression, fear, anger, hatred, etc.) gives an opportunity to solve problems. Art therapy technologies mainly consist of developing children and adolescents in need of help by pedagogues with the help of art therapy, their emotional and volitional sphere, cognitive processes, general characteristics. In these processes, the tasks of art therapy are mainly to adapt existing art therapy methods, and it is appropriate to use them in the

system of psycho-corrective work with children who need special help and their parents. In conclusion, it should be noted that the use of art therapy is the most effective method of social adaptation. Its inclusion in the field of education allows for full participation in the life of society, creativity of thinking and development of the integrity of the individual. Today, the "therapeutic effect with the help of visual arts" (painting, modeling, artistic crafts, etc.), which includes the most important stages in modern art therapy, is achieving positive results.

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THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

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